

Zvonik A.

Kharkiv State Academy of Design and Arts

Sahalovich A.

ООО «Навона»

ECONOMICS AND ENVIRONMENT. URGENCY IN INTEGRATION

UDC 330.366

ID ORCID 0000-0002-8218-4792

ID ORCID 0000-0001-6165-2801

Звоник А. А., Сагалович А. А. Економіка та екологія. Необхідність у взаємодії. Індустріальний період розвитку економіки характеризується необмеженим і неконтрольним вторгненням людини в природне середовище. Урбанізація населення відриває людину від її природних витоків, спотворює уявлення про єдину сутність природи і людини. Економічний розвиток земної цивілізації пов'язаний із прискоренням зростання споживання природних ресурсів планети, в результаті якого відбувається виснаження запасів природної сировини і погіршення стану навколишнього середовища як наслідок інтенсивного природокористування. Екології необхідний економічний погляд на проблему взаємовідносин людини і природи, на основі системи категорій економічної теорії як науки про принципи раціонального вибору в умовах обмеженості благ і ресурсів. Зараз суспільство і навколишнє природне середовище варто розглядати як складну соціально-еколого-економічну систему, у якій економічні, соціальні й екологічні питання мають розглядатися в єдиному комплексі.

Ключові слова: економіка, екологія, природокористування, економічна ефективність, ресурси.

Звоник А. А., Сагалович А. А. Экономика и экология. Необходимость во взаимодействии. Индустриальный период развития экономики характеризуется неограниченным и неконтрольным вторжением человека в природную среду. Урбанизация населения отрывает человека от его природных истоков, искажает представление о единой сущности природы и человека. Экономическое развитие земной цивилизации связано с ускорением роста потребления природных ресурсов планеты, в результате которого происходит истощение запасов природного сырья и ухудшение состояния окружающей среды как следствие интенсивного природопользования. Экологии необходим экономический взгляд на проблему взаимоотношений человека и природы, на основе системы категорий экономической теории как науки о принципах рационального выбора в условиях ограниченности благ и ресурсов. Сейчас общество и окружающую среду следует рассматривать как сложную социально-эколого-экономическую систему, в которой экономические, социальные и экологические вопросы должны рассматриваться в едином комплексе.

Ключевые слова: экономика, экология, природопользование, экономическая эффективность, ресурсы.

Economic science is one of the oldest. Interest in economic theory is due to the fact that it studies the problems of the decisive sphere of society – the production of economic goods, the exchange, distribution and consumption of national wealth in the material (housing, clothing, food, etc.) and non material (science, education, production experience, creative potential, etc.) forms, economic needs, interests of the person, as well as laws that govern these processes and which are embodied in the rational economic policy of the states.

The term “economy” comes from the Greek “oiconomia” (oikos – the house, the economy and nomos – the doctrine, the law), and it means, the economy in the original sense of the word is the science of household management.

Economic development had different stages during the historical development of mankind. At the moment, it is necessary to pay attention to the industrial period of economic development.

The industrial period of economic development is characterized by unrestricted and uncontrolled human invasion of the natural environment. In order to mechanize work, in huge quantities energy resources are consumed, natural landscapes that arise due to accumulation of waste in artificial landscapes, changing hydrogeological regimes of rivers, lakes and territories, changes in the climate and increasing reciprocal effects of the forces of nature. Urbanization of the population, separates a person from its natural origins, distorts the idea of a same essence of nature and man.

The economy will function normally if its components function properly. With this approach, natural living conditions are also included in natural resources.

It should be noted that there is no clear distinction between natural resources and natural conditions in real life.

There are three main factors in the development of the economy of any country:

- 1) labor resources;
- 2) means of production;
- 3) natural resources.

Economic development of civilization is associated with the acceleration of consumption of natural resources of the planet, which results in the depletion of reserves of non-renewable natural raw materials and the deterioration of the environment as a result of intensive nature use and its environmental impact.

The development of all living, human civilizations and states, each member of society directly or indirectly depends on the concentration, accessibility and use of natural resources. Formation and combination of natural resources predetermined the origin, diversity and evolution of forms of earthly life and the higher stage of development of their properties and states – psyche, consciousness, reason.

Thus, natural resources are the elements and forces of nature that a person uses or can use for his life's needs. Consequently, the use of nature is socio-economic and requires an integrated approach to its organization.

The relation to the natural environment is a measure of social and technical achievements

of human society, a characteristic of the level of civilization.

The main natural resources are: fertile land, air, seas, oceans, rivers, underground waters, flora and fauna, minerals.

At the initial stage of human development, the impact on nature was small. But the gradual development, which was accompanied by the involvement in the exploitation of natural resources, in the growing volumes and scales: land for agricultural production, livestock, industrial and non-productive construction; water resources for industrial and domestic needs, for irrigation of agricultural land, for the production of electricity; forest resources, depth of land; energy and mineral resources. The dominant principle of nature management has long remained the economic principle, according to which the criterion of the effectiveness of economic activity is the receipt of maximum economic benefits at minimal cost. The growth of the mass of resources used in production, with such an extensive method, goes without regard to the effectiveness of their use. (Tab. 1) With only the economic principle of environmental management, environmental problems are completely ignored, anthropogenic pressure is growing at a rapid pace.

According to the IEA from 1990 to 2008, the front use of energy per capita increased by 10 %, while the population increased by 27 %. Regional use of energy also has increased: in the Middle East – by 170 %, in China – by 146 %, in India – by 91 %, in Africa – by 70 %, in Latin America – by 66 %, in the USA by 20 %, in the EU-27 – by 7 %, and in the whole world – by 39 %.

In 2008, the total world energy consumption was 474 EJ ($474 \times 10^{18} \text{ J} = 132,000 \text{ TWh}$), which is equal to the average energy consumption of 15 TW. The annual renewable energy potential of renewable energy sources: solar energy – 1,775 EJ (438,000 TWh), wind energy – 640 EJ (178,000 TWh), geothermal energy – 5,000 EJ (1,390,000 TWh), biomass – 276 EJ (77,000 TWh), hydropower – 50 EJ (14,000 TW / year) and ocean energy – 1 EJ (280 TW / year). (Fig. 1)

Energy consumption in the G20 countries increased by more than 5 % in 2010 after a slight drop in 2009. In 2009, world energy consumption fell by –1.1 % (equivalent to 130 Mt of oil) for the first time in 30 years, as a result of the economic crisis, which reduced world GDP by 0.6 % in 2009. [12]

Energy consumption is poorly correlated with GDP and climate, but there is a big difference even among the most developed countries such as Japan and Germany, which consume 6 kW of energy per capita and the US with energy consumption of 11.4 kW per capita. In developing countries, especially those in subtropical and tropical latitudes, such as India, per capita energy consumption is about 0.7 kW. Bangladesh has a minimum power consumption of 0.2 kW per capita.

The US consumes 25 % of the world's energy, with 22 % of world GDP and 4.59 % of the world's population. [3] The most significant increase in energy consumption is currently in China, which

has grown by 5.5 % per year over the past 25 years. His population (1.3 billion people, 19.6 % of the world's population [3]) consumes 1.6 kW energy per capita. (Fig. 2)

The reduction in energy consumption was the result of two opposite trends: a significant increase in energy consumption in several developing countries, in particular in Asia (+ 4 %), and a decline in consumption in OECD countries by 4.7 % in 2009 to the level of 2000. In North America, Europe and the CIS, energy consumption fell by 4.5 %, 5 %, and 8.5 %, respectively, due to the slowdown in economic activity. China has become one of the world's largest energy consumer (18 % of the total), increasing it by 8 % in 2009 (4 % in 2008). Oil remained the most important energy resource with a share of 33 %, despite the fact that its share is constantly decreasing. (Fig. 3) Coal is gaining in increasing importance in world energy consumption: in 2009 its share amounted to 27 % of the total volume.

Most of the energy is consumed in producer countries, as it is cheaper to transport finished products than raw materials. In 2008, the share of exports in total energy production by type of fuel: oil – 50 % (1 952/3 941 Mt), gas – 25 % (800/3 149 billion m³), coal – 14 % (793/5 845 Mt) and electricity – 1 % (269/20 181 TW / year). [11]

Most of the world's energy resources consist of the transformation of solar energy on the surface of the planet into other forms. Part of this energy has been preserved in the form of fossil energy resources, a part that can be used directly or indirectly, for example, by wind, solar, hydro or wave power plants. The amount of energy measured by satellites is approximately equal to 1,368 W/m² [9] and varies by 6.9 % during the year due to the different distance of the Earth from the Sun. The total amount of solar energy received by the planet is approximately equal to 89 PW.

Estimates of the world's non-renewable energy reserves are different, while other sources of energy are estimated at 0.4 IJ (1 IJ = 1024 J), and available nuclear power resources such as uranium exceed 2.5 IJ. Fossil energy resources can be estimated at 0.6–3.0 IJ, if you include methane hydrate reserves, provided that they are technically available. The solar energy flow to Earth is 3.8 IJ / year, which is more than the stock of all non-renewable energy resources.

Since the end of 70's of the 20th century, when the imbalance in the geocosystems caused a huge economic loss, it was not safe at first in the use of nature, and then more widely began to introduce the ecological and economic principle of nature management, according to which the criterion for the effectiveness of economic activity is to obtain the maximum possible economic benefits with the least harmful impact on the natural environment.

Today, the course is aimed at sustainable development, the main components of which are: economic and environmental. The economy has an overall human background with ecology. They are closely interconnected.

Ecology requires an economic view of the problem of relationship between man and nature,

based on the system of categories of economic theory as a science of the principles of rational choice in the conditions of limited wealth and resources.

The concept of sustainable development is the result of rethinking man-made and noosphere civilization concepts of human development. Consequently, the word “stable” in the term “sustainable development” carries a double burden on itself. On the one hand – economic development, which ensures a stable state of the environment, on the other hand – sustainable economic growth. It follows that the ecology and economy must be considered in the system and properly managed by this system. Ecological-economic system – the economy of any region, whose elements of the structure act as economic, social, technological and natural processes occurring in it [1].

Management of the ecological-economic system represents an integral set of methods and tools of socio-economic and ecological management. In general, an effective approach in managing ecological and economic systems should take into account the specifics and rely on both administrative and control, economic, and socio-political, psychological, moral and ethical management tools. The approach to managing the ecological-economic system requires personnel, science and technology and information policies that are provided in the subsystems.

Ecologically stable economic development – socio-economic development, in which the meeting needs of the present generation of people is carried out with the condition of environmental constraints necessary to ensure the ability of future generations to meet their own needs [2].

The European Environment Agency (EEA) takes into account only final energy consumption (that is, it does not include energy lost in production and transmission of electricity) and believes that transport uses 31.5 % of final energy consumption, industry – 27.6 %, households – 25.9 %, services sector – 11.4 % and agriculture – 3.7 % [7]. Energy consumption is responsible for most of the greenhouse gas emissions – 79 %, with the energy sector responsible for 31 %, transport – 19 %, industry – 13 %, households – 9 %, others – 7 % [5].

In this situation some economic levers we should use. It can be sales of emission quotas, creation of environmental insurance funds, environmental leasing, mortgage system, compensation policy, accelerated depreciation method, tax exemptions, fees for environmental pollution and waste placement, compensatory payments for the disposal of natural resources from the target using them for deterioration of their quality and fees for the use of natural resources [10].

Natural use – the process of exploiting natural resources in order to meet the needs of society. The needs of mankind are not limited to a purely material sphere, therefore, the use of nature should include recreational activities aimed at improving the health of the population and increasing social and labor potential; the storage of objects of a living and inanimate nature that are especially valuable to humanity. Natural components can be applied to

people both in the role of natural resources and in the role of natural habitats.

Elements of nature, which are used by society in production and are its raw material and energy base, are called natural resources. Elements of nature that affect the lives and activities of people, but do not take part in material production, are considered as natural conditions.

Man influences natural resources, including them in their production activities, so the reserves of many of them are reduced and can later be completely exhausted. Implementation in practice in the 70's – early 80's of the ecological and economic method of nature use gave certain results, however, he was unable to resolve the existing contradiction between society and nature, because the concept of “the least harmful effects on the natural environment” is not very concrete and vague. It allows environmentalists to treat it too arbitrarily, to put the economic benefit at the forefront and to completely avoid the issue of the environmental plan. Therefore, in recent years, an increase in anthropogenic pressure on nature has continued as a result of ever-increasing production volumes, adding to the nature of all new natural objects, that is, the extensive method of socio-economic growth prevails.

At the present stage of the integration of nature and society, it becomes clear that for the preservation of the natural environment and the existence of life itself on the Earth, new approaches to the organization of productive activities are required, in which the natural cycles of matter and exchange-energy processes in the biosphere will not be violated. Nature use should be based on a new socioecological principle, in which the criterion of the effectiveness of economic activity to obtain the maximum possible economic benefits with the obligatory storage of dynamic equilibrium in geoeconomic systems, which is achieved not exceeding anthropogenic loads of maximum permissible levels.

We need to evolve, switch from raw material economy to service and technology, use natural resources wisely. The best way to do this is to create an ecological economy. Such an economy will become a real factor in the humanization of economic growth. Neo-Institutional direction in the economic theory – the lack of clearly established property rights to resources and environmental benefits. If this disadvantage is eliminated, as well as with a number of factors, maintaining the optimal quality of the environment can be provided on a market-based basis, and the state should only establish these market rights.

While energy efficiency is becoming increasingly important for public policy, more than 70 % of EU coal-fired power plants have an age of over 20 years and operate at an efficiency of 32–40 % [6]. Technological developments of the 1990's have allowed to increase efficiency to the level of 40–45 % in the new CHP. However, according to the European Commission's assessment, it is still below the level of the best available technology (NST), which has an efficiency of 46–49 %. The efficiency of the gas combustion plant is 52 % on average, compared

Tab. 1

Use of energy in the context of sources of migration, in 2000–2008, PWh [4]

	Comprehensive	Atomic	Renewable	Total
1990	83,37	6,11	13,08	102,57
2000	94,49	7,86	15,34	117,69
2008	117,08	8,28	18,49	143,85
Change 2000–2008	22,58	0,43	3,16	26,16

1 PWh = 1012 kWh

with 58–59 % to the best available technology. Gas and oil boilers operate at an average efficiency of 36 % (NST provides 47 %) [6]. According to the same assessment of the European Commission, the construction of new efficient CHP plants and increasing the efficiency of most existing CHP plants to an average efficiency of 51.5 % in 2020 will reduce the annual consumption of 15 billion m³ of natural gas and 25 million tons of coal [6].

More than \$ 1600 billion was invested in 2013 to provide consumers with energy in the world, twice as much as in 2000. 130 billion dollars is invested in energy efficiency. The role of renewable energy sources, the volume of investments in which amounted to \$ 60 billion in 2000, reached a maximum of \$ 300 billion in 2011 and amounted to \$ 250 billion in 2013. 1100 billion dollars was invested in the extraction and transportation of fossil fuels, oil refining and the construction of fossil fuel fired power plants [8].

The sociological principle of nature management requires the transition from irrational extensive nature use, in which the environmental protection is aimed at combating the negative effects of inappropriate nature management, to rational, equilibrium, in which society must control the conservation of nature and optimization of the human environment, so that there is no conflict between society and nature.

Now society and the environment should be considered as a complex socio-ecological and economic system, in which economic, social and environmental issues should be considered in a single complex.

The main task of the economy of nature management is the development of the best variants of adaptation of the global socio-ecological-economic system to the changes occurring in the biosphere, the definition of optimal anthropogenic loads on the natural environment, using all possible economic incentives.

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Fig. 1. World consumption of electricity [11]

Fig. 2. Map of world consumption of energy per capita [3]

Fig. 3. World use of energy in 1989–1999 [3]

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Рецензент статті: Откидач В. М., доктор мистецтвознавства, професор, Харківська державна академія культури

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